

WORKSHOP REPORT

T7 WORKSHOP ON PROVENANCE FOR TRANSPARENT RESEARCH

22 July 2021

Provenance Week 2021

www.t7-workshop.online

SUMMARY

The *T7 Workshop on Provenance for Transparent Research* was convened on July 22, 2021 as a half-day session at *Provenance Week 2021*. Held virtually, the meeting engaged 60 active participants worldwide representing the natural sciences, social sciences, data science, computer science, engineering, the humanities, and other disciplines. In a keynote presentation and seven lightning talks speakers explored the significance of terms such as *transparency*, *traceability*, and *trustworthiness* in the context of their respective disciplines, and highlighted how current and envisioned methods for provenance capture, representation, storage, and access promise to support these and other elements of research excellence. Workshop objectives included identifying needs of particular research communities and other stakeholders, prioritizing desiderata for real-world system implementations, and highlighting remaining challenges in the effort to make research fully transparent and support for scientific claims easier to evaluate.

All workshop attendees were encouraged to suggest definitions, insights, priorities, and general observations in the form of concise statements throughout the proceedings. These contributions were assessed by participants on a Likert-like scale. Poll results were displayed in real time and segmented by the disciplines represented by participants. Rather than exclusively seeking statements expected to find unanimous agreement, participants were urged to craft statements likely to yield *discordant* responses, with the aim of bringing to light differences between research disciplines potentially worthy of further investigation. Preliminary analysis indicates that 13 statements yielded such discordant responses; each of these statements received a minimum of 25% of votes on *both* sides of the agreement scale. Workshop organizers and attendees committed to further exploring the identified issues via a dedicated online forum.

PRESENTATIONS

The following are the titles, authors, and presenters (underlined) of the formal presentations made during the workshop.

Principles of Transparent Research: Implementation Challenges (keynote presentation)

Lars Vilhuber

Automated Screening of COVID-19 Preprints: Are We Helping authors Improve Transparency and Reproducibility?

Automated Screening Working Group, Anita Bandrowski

Persistent IDs and W3C PROV, or, Is W3C PROV FAIR?

Sadnan Al Manir, Justin Niestroy, Maxwell Adam Levinson, and Timothy Clark

Improving the Traceability of (Meta)Data Through Semantically Enriched Nanopublications

Matheus Pedra Puime Feijóó, Rodrigo Jardim, Sergio Manuel Serra da Cruz, Maria Luiza Campos

Enabling Trustworthy and Traceable Research by Non-Repudiable Opaque Provenance in a Distributed Environment

Rudolf Wittner, Jörg Geiger, Cecilia Mascia, Francesca Frexia, Heimo Muller, Petr Holub

Contemporary and Established Provenance Issues in Natural History Collections

Laurence Livermore, Ben Scott, Mathias Dillen

Auditable Spreadsheets

Laura Waltersdorfer, Fajar Ekaputra, Tomasz Miksa

From Traceability to Transparency of Bioinformatics Data Analyses: Round Trip?

Sarah Cohen-Boulakia

PARTICIPATION

A total of 60 attendees participated in the workshop polls. As shown below, 45 identified one or more disciplines with which they had experience, and separately indicated the one discipline they would represent in their responses to the polls throughout the workshop. The responses to all other polls were segmented by the latter identification.

The disciplinary areas I have experience in:

Mentimeter

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The one disciplinary area I represent today :

Mentimeter

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EXAMPLES OF CONCORDANT RESPONSES

Polls for a total of 15 statements collected at least 75% of the votes on one side of the agreement scale, and no more than 10% on the other. Four examples:

Verification and secondary review for transparency/computational reproducibility is expensive and time intensive.

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The one disciplinary area I represent today :

- biological science
- computer science
- data science
- engineering
- high performance computing
- humanities
- medical science
- physical science
- social science
- software development
- Unknown

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There is a role for automated provenance capture to simplify the verification process

Mentimeter

The one disciplinary area I represent today :

- biological science
- computer science
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- high performance computing
- humanities
- medical science
- physical science
- social science
- software development
- Unknown

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The IPAW community should actively find out why the popular WfMS don't use PROV

The one disciplinary area I represent today :

- biological science
- computer science
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- high performance computing
- humanities
- medical science
- physical science
- social science
- software development
- Unknown

We just need everyone in a particular community to adopt the same provenance-enabled computing platform.

The one disciplinary area I represent today :

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- medical science
- physical science
- social science
- software development
- Unknown

EXAMPLES OF DISCORDANT RESPONSES

Polls for a total of 13 statements yielded discordant responses with at least 25% of votes on each of the *agree* and *disagree* sides of the scale. Four examples:

Interoperability should be a primary goal of provenance

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All provenance collection should start at the questions users want to ask, not what is possible to be collected

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Traceability is more important than reproducibility, (PROV + FAIR enables traceability but not general reproducibility).

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- social science
- software development
- Unknown

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The guarantee of true scientific reproducibility is not our software, but natural laws. Science is a search for those things that are reproducible.

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The one disciplinary area I represent today :

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- physical science
- social science
- software development
- Unknown

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WORKSHOP ORGANIZERS

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